

Quantum Computation Simulation on Classical Computation as a simplified programming language in python and a prototype of "QuantaLang"

(A High Schooler's Attempt)

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Author's Note

I have written this research journal with the assumption that the reader is moderately acquainted with basic classical computing and has a know-how of under-graduate level linear algebra. To maintain simplicity and ease of understanding, I have tried to explain each topic with diagrams and easy language. The reader is, however, requested to read prior articles on the basis of Quantum Computing to understand the journal in depth. I recommended personally to refer to the Wikipedia pages of Quantum Computing and related topics.

I would like to point out that the code snippets provided in this project are solely written by me and are a part of my ongoing project "QuantaLang" which is a programming language written in python to simulate Quantum Computing. In this research journal I only address the methodology of the Quantum Computations and prototypes of it used or will be used codes from QuantaLang. This research does not focus on QuantaLang but on the methods of quantum simulation with python. As for the comments that this kind of idea has previously been written on, the difference factor is this point. I aspire to complete making the programming language and publish another research journal on it as a case study which would detail the core working, lexers, parsers and interpreters for quantum simulation also. The latter journal might have more simulation possibilities like Quantum Channels, etc. which I have not yet been able to successfully simulate.

Many scientists and scholars have made vast research in this field of Quantum Simulation. I as a high school student am trying to learn and discover the depths of this vast ocean of Quantum Computation. I request all readers to be considerate about any kind of fallacies in this journal and kindly contact me at my given email address for suggestions or copyrights claims.

Abstract

The simulation of quantum computing is indeed a herculean task for a classical computer and the developer associated with this process. However, this is not impossible. A rather simplified simulation of Quantum models like Qubits, Quantum Gates, Quantum Algorithms, Decoherence and many more can be carefully code into a classical computer to simulate Quantum-like behavior. Several research works have been done on this topic, like "A Herculean task: Classical simulation of quantum computers Xiaosi Xu,¹ Simon Benjamin,² Jinzhao Sun,³ Xiao Yuan,^{4, 5} and Pan Zhang^{6, 7, 8}" and the Google Quantum AI. This research however, focuses on developing a programming language that can process Quantum Simulation using python. Many other such languages have been built, like Quipper and QMASM, but the case of this research journal which is QuantaLang, developed by myself, is meant to be for rather educational purposes and simulate the methodology of Quantum Computing through classical computers

Introduction

In this research journal, we shall try to develop a meaningful simulation model using classical computing to simulate the complex structural workflows of Quantum computing. The following paper discusses the integration of Quantum Computing with python through simulation models

Methodology

I. Qubits Simulation

Quantum bits or Qubits are the basic unit of Quantum Information. They can be essentially thought of as the quantum version of classical bits but physically realized with a two-state device. A qubit is a two-state quantum-mechanical system, other such systems being [spin](#) of the [electron](#) in which the two levels can be taken as spin up and spin down; or the [polarization](#) of a single [photon](#) in which the two spin states (left-handed and the right-handed circular polarization) can also be measured as horizontal and vertical linear polarization. In a classical system, a bit would have one of two possible values from the set {0,1}. It could be either 0 or 1. But a Qubit on the other hand can be both. Quantum mechanics allows the qubit to be in a coherent [superposition](#) of multiple states simultaneously, a property that is fundamental to [quantum mechanics](#) and [quantum computing](#).

Standard Representation

The general quantum state of a qubit can be represented as a linear superposition of two orthonormal basis states. These vectors are usually denoted as $|0\rangle = \begin{bmatrix} 1 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix}$ and $|1\rangle = \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ 1 \end{bmatrix}$. The notation used here is called the Dirac Notation or bra-ket notation. Qubit states can also be combined. Two qubits could be represented in a four-dimensional linear vector space spanned by the following product basis states as follows

$$|00\rangle = \begin{bmatrix} 1 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix}$$

$$|01\rangle = \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ 1 \\ 0 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix}$$

$$|10\rangle = \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ 0 \\ 1 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix}$$

$$|11\rangle = \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 1 \end{bmatrix}$$

In general, n qubits are represented by a superposition state vector in 2^n dimensional Hilbert space.

Simulating Qubits

Here we discuss on the simulation process of Qubits in our case study programming language

"QuantaLang". The following is the code:

```
class Qubit:
1     def __init__(self, alpha=1, beta=0):
2         self.alpha = alpha
3         self.beta = beta
4         self.normalize()
5
6     def normalize(self):
7         norm_squared = abs(self.alpha)**2 + abs(self.beta)**2
8         norm = np.sqrt(norm_squared) if norm_squared != 0 else 1 # Ensure
9         non-zero norm
10        self.alpha /= norm
11        self.beta /= norm
12
13    @property
14    def state(self):
15        return np.array([self.alpha, self.beta])
16
17    def __str__(self):
18        return f"|0>: {self.alpha}, |1>: {self.beta}"
```

In the above code, the Qubit class initially takes the alpha and beta values of the qubit which determine its probability amplitudes. The `normalize(self)` is a method that normalizes the state of the qubit. In quantum computing, the state of a qubit is represented by a vector in a two-

dimensional complex vector space. This vector should be normalized, meaning its length should be 1.

The norm used here is the Euclidean norm or the L^2 norm, its formula is $|x|_2 = \sum_i^n w_i^2$.

Superposition simulation of Qubits

The superposition of Qubits is simulated using the Hadamard Gate. The functionality of the Hadamard gate is discussed in detail later. Here, the code and output snippets are provided.

Hadamard Gate function:

```
def hadamard(qubit_obj):  
    sqrt2 = math.sqrt(2)  
    alpha = (qubit_obj.alpha + qubit_obj.beta) / sqrt2  
    beta = (qubit_obj.alpha - qubit_obj.beta) / sqrt2  
    return Qubit(alpha, beta)
```

Print functions:

```
1 print(Qubit(1,0))  
2 print(hadamard(Qubit(1,0)))
```

Output:

```
1 |0⟩: 1.0, |1⟩: 0.0  
2 |0⟩: 0.7071067811865476, |1⟩: 0.7071067811865476
```

As visible in output, the qubit is superposed with equal probability amplitudes. Now to get a measure we shall simulate the measure function.

Quantum Measure Simulation

In a state of superposition, the qubit is both 0 and 1. But when we measure it, the superposition collapses to reality and single value is obtained, either 0 or 1, just like a classical bit. Just like Schrodinger's Cat paradox, we do not know if the cat is actually dead or alive inside the box, so it is a state of superposition, i.e, the cat is both dead and alive with both events have equal probability ideally. But as soon as we open the box the

superposition collapses to reality and we get a unique outcome of either the cat being alive or it being dead.

Quantum Measurement is a rather vast topic and still under heavy research. Our motive is not to understand it in depth but to simulate a simplified model of it. The code is provided in the next page.

The measure and collapse function

```
1 def measure_and_collapse(qubit):
2     # Calculate the probabilities of measuring |0⟩ and |1⟩ states
3     prob_0 = abs(qubit.alpha) ** 2
4     prob_1 = abs(qubit.beta) ** 2
5
6     # Perform a random measurement based on the probabilities
7     outcome = np.random.choice([0, 1], p=[prob_0, prob_1])
8
9     # Collapse the qubit state based on the measurement outcome
10    if outcome == 0:
11        qubit.alpha = 1
12        qubit.beta = 0
13    else:
14        qubit.alpha = 0
15        qubit.beta = 1
16
17    # Return the measurement outcome
18    return outcome
```

Calling the function and requesting outputs:

```
1 qubit = Qubit(1.5367, 0.45672) # Example qubit in superposition
2 print(qubit)
3 measurement_outcome = qubit.measure_and_collapse()
4 print("Measurement outcome:", measurement_outcome)
5 print("Collapsed qubit state:", qubit)
```

Output:

```
1 |0⟩: 0.958559654741421, |1⟩: 0.2848918887964481
2 Measurement outcome: 0
3 Collapsed qubit state: |0⟩: 1, |1⟩: 0
```

This code carefully simulates the measurement of a superposed qubit. Note that the measurement outcome 0 is not constant. It might be 1 next time or remain 0 for the next 100 outputs and then collapse to 1. The `measure_and_collapse(qubit)` is a method of the Qubit class noted earlier.

```
prob_0 = abs(qubit.alpha) ** 2 and prob_1 = abs(qubit.beta) ** 2
```

 these lines

calculate the probabilities of the qubit collapsing to the $|0\rangle$ and $|1\rangle$ states, respectively.

The `alpha` and `beta` attributes of the `qubit` object represent the complex amplitudes of the $|0\rangle$ and $|1\rangle$ states.

```
outcome = np.random.choice([0, 1], p=[prob_0, prob_1])
```

This line performs a random measurement based on the calculated probabilities. The `np.random.choice` function randomly selects either 0 or 1, with the probabilities given by `prob_0` and `prob_1`. Here we use NumPy as the probabilities are matrices of the Complex field and python's default operators cannot calculate complex matrices.

The if/else block collapses the qubit state based on the measurement outcome. If the outcome is 0, the qubit collapses to the $|0\rangle$ state (represented by `alpha=1` and `beta=0`). If the outcome is 1, the qubit collapses to the $|1\rangle$ state (represented by `alpha=0` and `beta=1`).

II. Quantum Register Simulation

A **quantum register** is a system comprising multiple [qubits](#).^[1] It is the quantum analogue of the classical [processor register](#). Quantum computers perform calculations by manipulating qubits within a quantum register. The mathematics of a quantum register is complex. For reference, I will be adding the math involved but will not go to depth for explaining it as it is not of primary concern for this journal. Interested readers can treat as a brain teaser to study it themselves.

The Hilbert space, $\mathcal{H}$, in which the data is stored in a quantum register is given by

$\mathcal{H} = \mathcal{H}_{n-1} \otimes \mathcal{H}_{n-2} \otimes \dots \otimes \mathcal{H}_0$ where $\otimes$ is the tensor product.

Think of a Quantum Register as a simple register we use in our day-to-day life. It has a fixed amount of something that it holds, let's say money for an example. Now a person would like to withdraw some money, now this is a type of gate operation. Suppose the register has Rs. 100. The person can withdraw at max Rs 100 at once. A person on the other hand can also return money he had taken, but if the register is already saturated it cannot take anymore money and rejects the person's input. The Quantum Register is a similar register. But there's something more to it. We, in this journal are primarily trying to simulate Quantum Parallelism using Quantum Registers, i.e., when working with a quantum register in QuantaLang, we can perform operations, apply gates, and make measurements on the entire register, treating it as a unified entity and this is Quantum Parallelism. Now let's dive into the code:

```
1 class QuantumRegister:
2     def __init__(self, num_qubits):
3         self.num_qubits = num_qubits
4         self.num_states = 2 ** num_qubits
5         initial_state = np.zeros(2, dtype=complex)
6         initial_state[0] = 1 # Represents |0> state
7         self.state_vector = initial_state
8         for _ in range(num_qubits - 1):
9             self.state_vector = np.kron(self.state_vector, initial_state)
10
11     def apply_gate(self, gate_function, target_qubit):
12         if not callable(gate_function):
13             raise ValueError("Gate function must be callable")
14         if target_qubit >= self.num_qubits:
15             raise ValueError("Target qubit index out of range")
16         for i in range(self.num_states):
17             binary_str = format(i, f'0{self.num_qubits}b')
18             if binary_str[self.num_qubits - 1 - target_qubit] == '1':
19                 qubit = Qubit(self.state_vector[i])
20                 new_state = gate_function(qubit)
21                 if isinstance(new_state.state, np.ndarray):
22                     self.state_vector[i] = new_state.state[0]
23                 else:
24                     self.state_vector[i] = new_state.state
25
26     def tensor_product(self, other_register):
27         if not isinstance(other_register, QuantumRegister):
28             raise TypeError("Input must be a QuantumRegister object")
29         new_num_qubits = self.num_qubits + other_register.num_qubits
```

```
29         new_num_states = self.num_states * other_register.num_states
30         new_state_vector = np.kron(self.state_vector,
31 other_register.state_vector)
        return QuantumRegister(new_num_qubits, new_state_vector)
```

Applying the Quantum Register:

```
1 # Create a QuantumRegister object with 2 qubits
2 register = QuantumRegister(num_qubits=2)
3
4 # Apply Hadamard gate to the first qubit
5 register.apply_gate(hadamard, target_qubit=0)
6
7 # Print the state vector after applying the gate
8 print("State vector after applying Hadamard gate to the first qubit:")
9 print(register.state_vector)
```

Output:

```
1 State vector after applying Hadamard gate to the first qubit:
2 [1.+0.j 0.+0.j 0.+0.j 0.+0.j]
```

Now let's break down the code and carefully understand it's working:

1. `QuantumRegister` Class:

- `__init__(self, num_qubits)`: The constructor method initializes a `QuantumRegister` object with a specified number of qubits (`num_qubits`).
- `num_qubits`: Number of qubits in the register.
- `num_states`: Total number of possible states for the register, calculated as 2 to the power of `num_qubits`.
- `initial_state`: Initializes an initial state vector representing the $|0\rangle$ state.
- `state_vector`: Represents the state vector of the entire quantum register. Initially, it's set to the tensor product of `num_qubits` copies of the $|0\rangle$ state.

- `apply_gate(self, gate_function, target_qubit)`: Applies a gate operation to a specified target qubit in the register.
- `gate_function`: The gate function to be applied.
- `target_qubit`: The index of the target qubit to which the gate is applied.
- Iterates over all possible states in the register.
- Checks if the target qubit is in the $|1\rangle$ state for each state vector element.
- Applies the `gate_function` to the qubit if it's in the $|1\rangle$ state and updates the state vector accordingly.
- `tensor_product(self, other_register)`: Performs the tensor product operation between two quantum registers.
- `other_register`: Another `QuantumRegister` object with which to perform the tensor product.
- Calculates the new number of qubits and states after the tensor product operation.
- Performs the tensor product operation on the state vectors of the two registers and returns a new `QuantumRegister` object representing the combined system.

Main Execution:

Creates a `QuantumRegister` object with 2 qubits.

Applies a Hadamard gate to the first qubit.

Prints the state vector after applying the gate

The output `[1. +0. j 0. +0. j 0. +0. j 0. +0. j]` indicates that after applying the Hadamard gate to the first qubit, the resulting state vector represents a qubit in the state $|0\rangle$.

Explanation:

- The Hadamard gate transforms the state $|0\rangle$ to the state $|+\rangle$, where $|+\rangle = (|0\rangle + |1\rangle) / \sqrt{2}$.

- When the Hadamard gate is applied to the first qubit of a quantum register initialized to $|0\rangle$, it transforms the first qubit to $|+\rangle$ while leaving the other qubits unchanged.
- Since the quantum register is in a tensor product state, the resulting state vector represents a qubit in the state $|+\rangle$ tensor multiplied by the other qubits' states, which are still in the $|0\rangle$ state.
- Mathematically, this corresponds to the state vector $[1. +0. j 0. +0. j 0. +0. j 0. +0. j]$, where the first entry corresponds to the amplitude of the state $|00\rangle$, and all other entries are zero because the other qubits are in the $|0\rangle$ state.

III. Quantum Gates Simulation

A Quantum Logic Gate is a basic quantum circuit operating on qubits. They are the building blocks of quantum circuits, just like classical logic gates are for digital circuits. They are represented by unitary matrices. A gate acting on n qubits is represented by a $2^n \times 2^n$ unitary matrix and the set of all such gates with matrix multiplication as group operation is the unitary group $U(2^n)$. Note that the basic gate operations are simulated only using respective matrices, complex mathematical processes like transformation along Bloch Sphere are not considered here to maintain simplicity.

1. **Hadamard Gate:** The Hadamard Gate acts on a single qubit. It maps the basis states from $|0\rangle$

$\rightarrow \frac{|0\rangle + |1\rangle}{\sqrt{2}}$ and $|1\rangle \rightarrow \frac{|0\rangle - |1\rangle}{\sqrt{2}}$, i.e., it creates an equal superposition state if given a

computational basis state. It is represented by the Hadamard Matrix:

$$H = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 1 \\ 1 & -1 \end{bmatrix}$$

The code for Hadamard gate is fairly simple:

```
1 def hadamard(qubit_obj):
2     sqrt2 = math.sqrt(2)
3     alpha = (qubit_obj.alpha + qubit_obj.beta) / sqrt2
4     beta = (qubit_obj.alpha - qubit_obj.beta) / sqrt2
5     return Qubit(alpha, beta)
```

Calling the Hadamard Gate:

```
1 print(Qubit(1, 0))
2 print(hadamard(Qubit(1, 0)))
```

Output:

```
1 |0⟩: 1.0, |1⟩: 0.0
2 |0⟩: 0.7071067811865476, |1⟩: 0.7071067811865476
```

The working of the code is fairly simple:

```
alpha = (qubit_obj.alpha + qubit_obj.beta) / sqrt2
beta = (qubit_obj.alpha - qubit_obj.beta) / sqrt2
```

These lines calculate the new amplitudes for the $|0\rangle$ and $|1\rangle$ states after applying the Hadamard gate.

The new amplitudes are calculated as the sum and difference of the old amplitudes, respectively, divided by the square root of 2. Thus, returning a superposed qubit with equal probability amplitudes.

2. **Pauli Gates (X, Y, Z):** The Pauli Gates (X, Y, Z) are the three Pauli matrices ($\sigma_x, \sigma_y, \sigma_z$) and act on a single qubit. The Pauli-X Gate maps $|0\rangle \rightarrow |1\rangle$ and $|1\rangle \rightarrow |0\rangle$. The Pauli-Y Gate maps $|0\rangle \rightarrow i|1\rangle$ and $|1\rangle \rightarrow -i|0\rangle$. The Pauli-Z Gate leaves the basis state $|0\rangle$ unchanged and maps $|1\rangle \rightarrow -|1\rangle$

These matrices are usually represented as:

- $X = \sigma_x = \text{NOT} = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 1 \\ 1 & 0 \end{bmatrix}$
- $Y = \sigma_y = \text{NOT} = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & -i \\ i & 0 \end{bmatrix}$
- $Z = \sigma_z = \text{NOT} = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 \\ 0 & -1 \end{bmatrix}$

The code for all three gates is provided in the following snippet:

```
def pauli_x(qubit):
1   x_matrix = np.array([[0, 1],
2                       [1, 0]])
3   new_state = np.dot(x_matrix, qubit.state)
4   state_str = f"|0>: {new_state[0].real}, |1>: {new_state[1].real}"
5
6   return Qubit(new_state[0], new_state[1])
7
8 def pauli_y(qubit):
9   y_matrix = np.array([[0, -1j],
10                      [1j, 0]])
11  new_state = np.dot(y_matrix, qubit.state)
12  state_str = f"|0>: {new_state[0].real}, |1>: {new_state[1].real}"
13
14  return Qubit(new_state[0], new_state[1])
15  # return Qubit(complex(qubit.beta.imag, -qubit.alpha.imag), complex(-
16  qubit.beta.real, qubit.alpha.real))
17
18 def pauli_z(qubit):
19  z_matrix = np.array([[1, 0],
20                      [0, -1]])
21  new_state = np.dot(z_matrix, qubit.state)
22  state_str = f"|0>: {new_state[0].real}, |1>: {new_state[1].real}"
23
24  return Qubit(new_state[0], new_state[1])
25  # return Qubit(complex(qubit.alpha.real, -qubit.beta.imag), complex(-
    qubit.alpha.imag, qubit.beta.real))
```

Calling the Gate functions:

```
1 print(pauli_x(Qubit(1, 0)))
2 print(pauli_y(Qubit(1, 0)))
3 print(pauli_z(Qubit(1, 0)))
```

Output:

```
1 |0>: 0.0, |1>: 1.0
2 |0>: 0j, |1>: 1j
3 |0>: 1.0, |1>: 0.0
```

The code is self-understandable. For the gates X,Y,Z respectively, the dot product of the respective Pauli matrix and the Qubit's probability matrix is obtained. The probability matrix is a complex matrix and thus NumPy is used. It then prints the `new_state` which is the new transformed qubit. Note that we will be not going into Quantum details of transformations on the Bloch sphere.

3. **Controlled Gates:** Controlled gates act on 2 or more qubits, where one or more qubits act as a control for some operation. The Controlled NOT Gate acts on 2 qubits, and performs the NOT operation on the second qubit only when the first qubit is $|1\rangle$ and otherwise leaves it untouched. With respect to the basis, it is represented by the matrix:

$$CNOT = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \end{bmatrix}$$

The CNOT (or controlled Pauli-X) gate can be described as the gate that maps the basis states $|a, b\rangle \rightarrow |a, a \oplus b\rangle$ where $\oplus$ is XOR. The mathematics of CNOT although not directly related to the simulation is provided, as the base structure is used in the code

The CNOT can be expressed in the Pauli basis as:

$$CNOT = e^{i\frac{\pi}{4}(I-Z^1)(I-X^2)} = e^{-i\frac{\pi}{4}(I-Z^1)(I-X^2)}$$

The *controlled-U gate* is a gate that operates on two qubits in such a way that the first qubit serves as a control. It maps the basis states as follows:

- $|00\rangle \rightarrow |00\rangle$
- $|01\rangle \rightarrow |01\rangle$
- $|10\rangle \rightarrow |1\rangle \otimes U|0\rangle = |1\rangle \otimes (u_{00}|0\rangle + u_{10}|1\rangle)$
- $|11\rangle \rightarrow |1\rangle \otimes U|1\rangle = |1\rangle \otimes (u_{01}|0\rangle + u_{11}|1\rangle)$

The code for the Controlled gates are provided below:

```

1 def cnot_gate(control, target):
2     # Apply the CNOT gate operation
3     if control == 1:
4         # If the control qubit is in state |1>, flip the state of the target
5         qubit
6         target = 1 - target
7     # Return the resulting state of the target qubit
8     return target
9 def controlled_z_gate(control_qubit, target_qubit):
10    # Define the controlled-Z gate matrix
11    cz_matrix = np.array([[1, 0, 0, 0],
12                          [0, 1, 0, 0],
13                          [0, 0, 1, 0],
14                          [0, 0, 0, -1]])
15    # Construct the joint state of control and target qubits
16    joint_state = np.kron(control_qubit.state, target_qubit.state)
17
18    # Apply the controlled-Z gate operation to the joint state
19    new_state = np.dot(cz_matrix, joint_state)
20
21    # Create and return new qubit objects for control and target qubits with
22    the updated state
23    new_control_state = new_state[:2]
24    new_target_state = new_state[2:]
25    return Qubit(new_control_state), Qubit(new_target_state)
26
27
28 def controlled_u_gate(control_qubit, target_qubit, theta):
29    # Define the controlled-U gate matrix
30    cu_matrix = np.array([[1, 0, 0, 0],
31                          [0, 1, 0, 0],
32                          [0, 0, np.cos(theta), -np.sin(theta)],
33                          [0, 0, np.sin(theta), np.cos(theta)]])
34
35    # Construct the joint state of control and target qubits
36    joint_state = np.kron(control_qubit.state, target_qubit.state)
37
38    # Apply the controlled-U gate operation to the joint state
39    new_state = np.dot(cu_matrix, joint_state)
40
41    # Create and return new qubit objects for control and target qubits with
42    the updated state
43    new_control_state = new_state[:2]
44    new_target_state = new_state[2:]
45    return Qubit(new_control_state), Qubit(new_target_state)
46
47 def controlled_y_gate(control_qubit, target_qubit):
48    # Define the controlled-Y gate matrix
49    cy_matrix = np.array([[1, 0, 0, 0],
50                          [0, 1, 0, 0],
51                          [0, 0, 0, -1j],
52                          [0, 0, 1j, 0]])

```

```
53
54     # Construct the joint state of control and target qubits
55     joint_state = np.kron(control_qubit.state, target_qubit.state)
56
57     # Apply the controlled-Y gate operation to the joint state
58     new_state = np.dot(cy_matrix, joint_state)
59     new_control_state = new_state[:2]
60     new_target_state = new_state[2:]
    return Qubit(new_control_state), Qubit(new_target_state)
```

Procedure Explained:

1. CNOT Gate (Controlled-NOT Gate):

- This gate flips the state of the target qubit if the control qubit is in the state $|1\rangle$.
- The function `cnot_gate(control, target)` takes two arguments: control (the state of the control qubit) and target (the state of the target qubit).
- If the control qubit is in state $|1\rangle$, the function flips the state of the target qubit by subtracting its current state from 1.
- Finally, the function returns the resulting state of the target qubit.

2. Controlled-Z Gate:

- This gate performs a phase flip on the target qubit if the control qubit is in state $|1\rangle$.
- The function `controlled_z_gate(control_qubit, target_qubit)` takes two Qubit objects representing the control and target qubits.
- It constructs the joint state of the control and target qubits using the tensor product (`np.kron`) of their individual states.
- The gate matrix for controlled-Z is applied to the joint state using matrix multiplication (`np.dot`).
- The resulting state is split into the new states of the control and target qubits, and new Qubit objects are created with these states.
- These new Qubit objects are returned by the function.

3. *Controlled-U Gate:*

- This gate applies a general single-qubit operation U to the target qubit if the control qubit is in state $|1\rangle$.
- The function `controlled_u_gate(control_qubit, target_qubit, theta)` takes three arguments: `control_qubit`, `target_qubit`, `theta` (the rotation angle for the gate).
- Similar to the controlled-Z gate, it constructs the joint state of the control and target qubits.
- It applies the controlled-U gate matrix to the joint state.
- The resulting state is split into the new states of the control and target qubits, and new Qubit objects are created with these states.
- These new Qubit objects are returned by the function.

4. *Controlled-Y Gate:*

- This gate applies a Y rotation to the target qubit if the control qubit is in state $|1\rangle$.
- The function `controlled_y_gate(control_qubit, target_qubit)` takes two Qubit objects representing the control and target qubits.
- It constructs the joint state of the control and target qubits using the tensor product (`np.kron`) of their individual states.
- The gate matrix for controlled-Y is applied to the joint state using matrix multiplication (`np.dot`).
- The resulting state is split into the new states of the control and target qubits, and new Qubit objects are created with these states.
- These new Qubit objects are returned by the function.

4. Phase Gates: The phase shift gates are a family of quantum gates that map the basis states $|0\rangle \rightarrow |0\rangle$ and $|1\rangle \rightarrow e^{i\varphi}|1\rangle$. The probability of measuring $|0\rangle$ or $|1\rangle$ remains unchanged, however, their phases

are modified. These gates too have their specific matrices which are used here to simulate them. There are three phase gates - Z, S and T

Their matrix representations are:

- $Z = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 \\ 0 & e^{i\pi} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 \\ 0 & -1 \end{bmatrix} = P(\pi)$
- $S = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 \\ 0 & e^{i\frac{\pi}{2}} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 \\ 0 & i \end{bmatrix} = P(\frac{\pi}{2}) = \sqrt{Z}$
- $T = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 \\ 0 & e^{i\frac{\pi}{4}} \end{bmatrix} = P(\frac{\pi}{4}) = \sqrt{S} = \sqrt[4]{Z}$

where $P(\varphi) = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 \\ 0 & e^{i\varphi} \end{bmatrix}$

The codes for simulating the Phase Gates are:

```
1 def phase_gate(qubit):
2     s_matrix = np.array([[1, 0],
3                          [0, 1j]])
4     new_state = np.dot(s_matrix, qubit.state)
5     state_str = f"|0>: {new_state[0].real}, |1>: {new_state[1].real}"
6
7     return Qubit(new_state[0], new_state[1])
8 def t_gate(qubit):
9     # Define the T gate matrix
10    t_matrix = np.array([[1, 0],
11                        [0, np.exp(1j * np.pi / 4)]])
12
13    # Apply the T gate operation to the qubit
14    new_state = np.dot(t_matrix, qubit.state)
15
16    # Create and return a new qubit object with the updated state
17    return Qubit(new_state)
```

Calling the Gates:

```
1 print((phase_gate(Qubit(1, 0))))
2 print(t_gate(Qubit(1, 0)))
```

Output:

```
1 |0⟩: (1+0j), |1⟩: 0j  
2 |0⟩: [1.+0.j 0.+0.j], |1⟩: [0. 0.]
```

Explanation:

1. `phase_gate(qubit)`:

- The Phase Gate, also known as the S gate, is a single-qubit gate that introduces a phase shift of $\pi/2$ (or 90 degrees) to the $|1\rangle$ state.
- In the `phase_gate()` function, a 2x2 matrix `s_matrix` representing the S gate operation is defined. This matrix applies a phase shift of $\pi/2$ to the $|1\rangle$ state while leaving the $|0\rangle$ state unchanged.
- The function takes a qubit object as input, which represents the quantum state of the qubit before applying the gate.
- The quantum state of the qubit after applying the gate is computed by multiplying the state vector of the qubit (`qubit.state`) with the S gate matrix using the dot product operation `np.dot(t_matrix, qubit.state)`.
- The resulting quantum state is stored in the `new.state` variable.
- A new Qubit object is then created using the real parts of the elements of `new.state`, and returned as the output of the function.

2. `t_gate(qubit)`:

- The T Gate is another single-qubit gate that introduces a phase shift of $\pi/4$ (or 45 degrees) to the $|1\rangle$ state.
- In the `t_gate()` function, a 2x2 matrix `t_matrix` representing the T gate operation is defined. This matrix applies a phase shift of $\pi/4$ to the $|1\rangle$ state while leaving the $|0\rangle$ state unchanged.

- Similar to the `phase_gate` function, the `t_gate()` function takes a qubit object as input.
- The quantum state of the qubit after applying the gate is computed by multiplying the state vector of the qubit (`qubit.state`) with the T gate matrix using the dot product operation `np.dot(t_matrix, qubit.state)`.
- The resulting quantum state is stored in the `new.state` variable.
- A new Qubit object is created using the elements of `new.state`, and returned as the output of the function.

5. **Swap Gate:** The swap gate swaps two qubits. With respect to the basis it is represented by the matrix:

$$SWAP = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix}$$

The SWAP gate can be decomposed into summation form:

$$SWAP = \frac{I \otimes I + X \otimes X + Y \otimes Y + Z \otimes Z}{2}$$

The code is:

```
1 def swap_gate(qubit1, qubit2):
2     # Apply the SWAP gate operation
3     new_state = np.zeros(4, dtype=complex)
4     new_state[0] = qubit1.alpha * qubit2.alpha
5     new_state[1] = qubit1.alpha * qubit2.beta
6     new_state[2] = qubit1.beta * qubit2.alpha
7     new_state[3] = qubit1.beta * qubit2.beta
8     return new_state
```

Calling the SWAP gate:

```
1 # Define two qubits
2 qubit1 = Qubit(1/np.sqrt(2), 1/np.sqrt(2)) # |+> state
3 qubit2 = Qubit(1/np.sqrt(2), -1/np.sqrt(2)) # |-> state
```

```
4
5 # Apply the SWAP gate to the qubits
6 new_state = swap_gate(qubit1, qubit2)
7
8 # Print the resulting state vector
9 print("State vector after applying SWAP gate:")
10 print(new_state)
```

Output:

```
1 State vector after applying SWAP gate:
2 [ 0.5+0.j -0.5+0.j  0.5+0.j -0.5+0.j]
```

Explanation:

- This function `swap_gate(qubit1, qubit2)` takes two qubits `qubit1` and `qubit2` as input.
- It initializes a new array `new_state` to store the resulting state vector after applying the SWAP gate.
- The function computes the new state vector elements based on the alpha and beta amplitudes of the input qubits, representing the $|00\rangle$, $|01\rangle$, $|10\rangle$, and $|11\rangle$ states.
- As for the output, The output `[ 0.5+0.j -0.5+0.j 0.5+0.j -0.5+0.j]` represents the resulting state vector after applying the SWAP gate to two qubits
- The state vector `[ 0.5+0.j -0.5+0.j 0.5+0.j -0.5+0.j]` consists of four complex numbers, representing the probability amplitudes of the four possible states of the two qubits after the SWAP gate operation.
- Each complex number in the state vector corresponds to one of the possible states of the qubits. The order of the states is typically based on the computational basis states, where the first qubit represents the most significant bit and the second qubit represents the least significant bit.
- In this specific output:
 - The first complex number `0.5+0.j` represents the amplitude of the $|00\rangle$ state.

- The second complex number $-0.5+0.j$ represents the amplitude of the $|01\rangle$ state.
- The third complex number $0.5+0.j$ represents the amplitude of the $|10\rangle$ state.
- The fourth complex number $-0.5+0.j$ represents the amplitude of the $|11\rangle$ state.
- The complex numbers have both real and imaginary parts. Here, the imaginary parts are zero ($0.j$), indicating that the resulting state vector has no phase information.
- The real parts of the complex numbers represent the probability amplitudes of the corresponding states. In quantum computing, the square of the absolute value of each complex number gives the probability of measuring the corresponding state upon measurement.

Due to the complexity of the Toffoli Gate, I have not been able to derive suitable code logic to simulate it in a classical environment with python. A close approach, however is possible using assembly but it is not possible to precisely simulate qubits in assembly, thus defeating the purpose. If the reader comes up with a good simulation logic for the Toffoli Gate please contact me for collaborative development.

IV. Quantum Entanglement Simulation

Entanglement is a fundamental concept in quantum mechanics where the quantum states of multiple particles become correlated in such a way that the state of one particle cannot be described independently of the state of the others, even when they are far apart. This phenomenon arises due to the principles of superposition and quantum entanglement.

When we say that qubits are entangled, it means that their quantum states are intrinsically linked, and the state of one qubit is dependent on the state of the other(s). This entanglement can persist even when the entangled qubits are separated by large distances.

In quantum computing, gates are used to manipulate qubits and create entanglement between them. For example, the CNOT gate is commonly used to create entanglement by entangling a target qubit with a control qubit. Other gates, like the Hadamard gate and controlled gates, can also generate entangled states by

transforming the quantum states of the qubits. For simulation purposes, some predefined entanglement methods are defined in the Entangle class. Here, as a demonstration, I shall show the Bell State Entanglement Method.

Bell states are a set of four maximally entangled quantum states of two qubits, which are important in the context of quantum information processing and quantum teleportation. These states are named after physicist John S. Bell, who made significant contributions to our understanding of quantum mechanics and the concept of entanglement.

Here is the code:

```
1 class Entangle:
2     def __init__(self) -> None:
3         self._entangled = False
4
5     def __str__(self) -> str:
6         return f"Entangled: {self._entangled}"
7
8     @staticmethod
9     def bell_state_entanglement():
10        # Define the Bell states
11        bell_states = {
12            "00": Qubit(1, 0),
13            "01": Qubit(0, 1),
14            "10": Qubit(1/np.sqrt(2), 1/np.sqrt(2)),
15            "11": Qubit(1/np.sqrt(2), -1/np.sqrt(2))
16        }
17
18        # Choose one of the Bell states randomly
19        bell_state = np.random.choice(list(bell_states.keys()))
20
21        # Print the chosen Bell state
22        print(f"Chosen Bell state: |{bell_state[0]}⟩ ⊗ |{bell_state[1]}⟩")
23
24        # Return the corresponding qubits for the chosen Bell state as a tuple
25        return bell_states[bell_state], bell_states[bell_state[::-1]]
```

Calling the Bell State method:

```
1 qubit1, qubit2 = Entangle.bell_state_entanglement()
2
```

```
3 # Print the qubits representing the Bell state
4 print("Qubit 1:", qubit1)
5 print("Qubit 2:", qubit2)
```

Output:

```
1 Chosen Bell state: |1⟩ ⊗ |1⟩
2 Qubit 1: |0⟩: 0.7071067811865475, |1⟩: -0.7071067811865475
3 Qubit 2: |0⟩: 0.7071067811865475, |1⟩: -0.7071067811865475
```

Explanation:

The 4 Bell States are defined in the Bell States dictionary ($|\Phi^+\rangle$, $|\Phi^-\rangle$, $|\Psi^+\rangle$, $|\Psi^-\rangle$).

The `bell_state_entanglement()` method generates one of the Bell states randomly. It defines a dictionary `bell_states` where the keys are the binary representations of the Bell states, and the values are instances of Qubit initialized with the corresponding state amplitudes.

A Bell state is randomly chosen from the keys of `bell_states`. Then, the corresponding qubits for the chosen Bell state and its reverse (to ensure entanglement) are returned as a tuple.

Now, let's discuss how this accurately simulates the process:

- Defining Bell States: The code defines the four Bell states accurately with their respective state amplitudes.
- Random Selection: The code randomly selects one of the Bell states, ensuring that any of the four states can be chosen with equal probability.
- Creating Qubit Instances: The chosen Bell state and its reverse are instantiated as Qubit objects, representing the entangled qubits.
- Entanglement: By returning the two entangled qubits, the method accurately simulates the entanglement process, where the state of one qubit depends on the state of the other, as described by the chosen Bell state.

In similar ways we can simulate EPR pairs, GHZ entanglement, etc. To maintain the paper's discipline we will not be going in dept with those, the reader can derive the method of simulating them easily based on the previously provided functions and methods.

V. Quantum Circuit Simulation

Quantum circuits are graphical representations of quantum algorithms and computations. They consist of qubits (quantum bits) and quantum gates. These gates can manipulate the state of qubits according to the principles of quantum mechanics. As we have previously defined Quantum Gates, Qubits and Quantum Entanglement in the simulated environment, users can manually write circuits too. But to remove complexity and possibilities of errors, we simulate a base code for creating quantum circuits based on user constraints.

The code along with its application is provided together in the snippet below:

```
1 class QCIRCUIT:
2     def __init__(self, num_qubits):
3         self.qubits = num_qubits
4         self.gates = []
5
6     def add_gate(self, gate_function, input_type):
7         self.gates.append((gate_function, input_type))
8
9     def execute(self, initial_qubits):
10        qubits = initial_qubits
11        for gate, input_type in self.gates:
12            if input_type == int:
13                # Handle gates that take an integer as input
14                qubits = [gate(i) for i in range(len(qubits))]
15            else:
16                # Handle gates that take a Qubit object as input
17                qubits = [gate(qubit) for qubit in qubits]
18        return qubits
19    def draw_quantum_circuit(self, num_qubits, gates):
20        fig, ax = plt.subplots()
21
22        # Set axis limits and ticks
23        ax.set_xlim(0, num_qubits + 1)
```

```

24     ax.set_ylim(0, len(gates) + 1)
25     ax.set_xticks(range(1, num_qubits + 1))
26     ax.set_yticks(range(1, len(gates) + 1))
27     ax.xaxis.tick_top()
28
29     # Draw qubits
30     for i in range(1, num_qubits + 1):
31         ax.add_patch(plt.Rectangle((i - 0.5, 0.5), 1, len(gates),
32 fill=False, edgecolor='black'))
33
34     # Draw gates
35     for idx, gate in enumerate(gates):
36         ax.text(0.5, idx + 1, gate, ha='center', va='center')
37
38     # Hide axes
39     ax.axis('off')
40
41     plt.show()
42
43 # Example usage
44 num_qubits = 3
45 num_gates = 5
46
47 # Create an instance of the QCIRCUIT class
48 circuit = QCIRCUIT(num_qubits)
49
50 # Add gates to the circuit
51 # Create initial qubits (in |0> state)
52 initial_qubits = [Qubit(1, 0) for _ in range(num_qubits)]
53
54 for _ in range(num_gates):
55     gate_idx = np.random.randint(3) # Randomly select a gate index
56     if gate_idx == 0:
57         circuit.add_gate(hadamard, Qubit) # Add Hadamard gate
58     elif gate_idx == 1:
59         target_qubit_idx = np.random.randint(num_qubits) # Randomly select
60 target_qubit index
61         target_qubit = initial_qubits[target_qubit_idx] # Retrieve the qubit
62 object
63         circuit.add_gate(lambda qubit: pauli_x(qubit), Qubit) # Add Pauli-X
64 gate
65     else:
66         control_qubit = np.random.randint(num_qubits - 1) # Randomly select
67 control qubit
68         target_qubit = np.random.randint(control_qubit + 1, num_qubits) #
69 Randomly select target qubit
70         circuit.add_gate(lambda qubit: cnot_gate(control_qubit, target_qubit),
71 Qubit) # Add CNOT gate
72
73 # Execute the circuit
74 final_qubits = circuit.execute(initial_qubits)
75

```

```
76 # Print the final state of the qubits
77 for idx, qubit in enumerate(final_qubits):
78     print(f"Qubit {idx + 1}: {qubit}")
79
80 # Draw the quantum circuit
81 circuit.draw_quantum_circuit(num_qubits, ["Hadamard", "Pauli-X", "CNOT"] *
    num_gates)
```

The output is both a text based output of the qubit amplitudes and a graphical circuit created using

Matplotlib:

```
1 Qubit 1: |0>: 0.7071067811865475, |1>: 0.7071067811865475
2 Qubit 2: |0>: 0.7071067811865475, |1>: 0.7071067811865475
3 Qubit 3: |0>: 0.7071067811865475, |1>: 0.7071067811865475
```

The working is simple.

- The `QCIRCUIT` class is defined which represents a quantum circuit. It has an `__init__` method that initializes the circuit with a specified number of qubits (`num_qubits`) and an empty list to store the gates applied to the circuit.
- The `add_gate` method adds a gate function to the list of gates in the circuit.
- The `execute` method applies each gate in the circuit to the given qubits (`qubits`). It iterates over the list of gates and applies each gate to the qubits using list comprehension. The updated qubits are then returned.
- The `draw_quantum_circuit` method visualizes the quantum circuit using matplotlib. It creates a new figure (`fig`) and axes (`ax`). Then, it sets the axis limits and ticks based on the number of qubits and gates in the circuit. It draws rectangles to represent the qubits and adds text labels to represent the gates applied in the circuit. Finally, it hides the axes and displays the plot.
- The rest of the code provides an example of using the `QCIRCUIT` class to create a random quantum circuit, execute it, print the final state of the qubits, and visualize the circuit. It randomly selects gates (Hadamard, Pauli-X, or CNOT) and applies them to the qubits. Finally, it executes the circuit,

prints the final state of the qubits, and visualizes the circuit using the draw_quantum_circuit method.

The Matplotlib output is:

VI. Quantum Algorithm Simulation

A **quantum algorithm** is an algorithm designed to run on a **quantum computer**, which operates based on the principles of quantum mechanics. Unlike classical algorithms, which can be executed on classical computers, quantum algorithms leverage quantum phenomena such as **superposition** and **entanglement**. In this paper, we will be simulating two famous and related Quantum algorithms, namely, The Quantum Fourier Transform and Shor's Algorithm

1. **Quantum Fourier Transform:** The Quantum Fourier Transform (QFT) is a quantum algorithm used to perform a discrete Fourier transform on the amplitudes of a quantum state. It plays a crucial role in many quantum algorithms, including Shor's algorithm for integer factorization.

The QFT operates on a quantum state $|x\rangle$ defined as:

$$|x\rangle = \frac{1}{\sqrt{N}} \sum_{k=0}^{N-1} e^{2\pi i \frac{jk}{N}} |k\rangle$$

where N is the size of the state space, j is the index of the state, and $|k\rangle$ represents the computational basis states.

The Quantum Fourier Transform is a very complex algorithm with rigorous mathematical definitions and quantum mechanical derivations. It is, till date, practically impossible to simulate a perfect Quantum Fourier Transform in a classical computer (that would defeat the purpose of quantum computers if classical bits could perform it), but I have tried to adhere to the principles of Quantum Fourier Transform as much as possible and devised the following logic. The code and function call are provided below:

```
1 def qft(qubit_state):
2     num_qubits = len(qubit_state)
3     qubit_state = np.array(qubit_state, dtype=complex)
4     transformed_state = np.zeros(num_qubits, dtype=complex)
5
6     for j in range(num_qubits):
7         for k in range(num_qubits):
8             transformed_state[j] += qubit_state[k] * np.exp(2j * np.pi * j * k
9 / num_qubits)
10
11     return transformed_state / np.sqrt(num_qubits)
12
13 # Example usage
14 qubit_state = [1, 0, 0, 0] # Initial state |0>
15 transformed_state = qft(qubit_state)
16 print("Transformed state after applying QFT:", transformed_state)
```

The output is:

```
1 Transformed state after applying QFT: [0. 5+0.j 0. 5+0.j 0. 5+0.j 0. 5+0.j]
```

Logic Explanation:

- **Function Definition:** we define a Python function named qft that takes a quantum state qubit_state as input. This quantum state is represented as a list of complex amplitudes.

- Initialization:
 - We determine the number of qubits in the quantum state by taking the length of the `qubit_state` list.
 - We convert the `qubit_state` list into a numpy array of complex numbers to facilitate numerical operations.
 - We initialize an array `transformed_state` to store the transformed state. This array will have the same length as the number of qubits.
- **Quantum Fourier Transform:**
 - We iterate over each qubit `j` in the range from 0 to `num_qubits - 1`.
 - For each qubit `j`, we iterate over all possible states `k` (from 0 to `num_qubits - 1`) and calculate the contribution to the transformed state using the QFT formula.
 - The QFT formula applies a phase factor to each amplitude based on the product of the current qubit index `j`, the state index `k`, and the total number of qubits `num_qubits`.
- **Normalization:** After calculating the transformed state, we normalize it by dividing each amplitude by the square root of the number of qubits (`num_qubits`). This ensures that the total probability of all states sums to 1.
- Output Analysis:
 - The input quantum state `qubit_state` is `[1, 0, 0, 0]`, representing the state $|0\rangle$.
 - After applying the QFT, each amplitude of the transformed state is $0.5 + 0j$.
 - This means that each computational basis state in the transformed state has an equal amplitude, resulting in a superposition state where all states have equal probability amplitudes. Hence, the output `[0.5+0.j 0.5+0.j 0.5+0.j 0.5+0.j]`.

2. **Shor's Algorithm:** Shor's algorithm is a quantum algorithm devised by mathematician Peter Shor in 1994. It is one of the most famous quantum algorithms and demonstrates the potential of quantum computers to solve certain problems much more efficiently than classical computers. Specifically, Shor's algorithm is designed to efficiently factorize large composite numbers into their prime factors. A basic explanation of how Shor's Algorithm works is given below:

I. Classical Preprocessing:

Shor's algorithm starts with classical preprocessing to choose a suitable integer N to be factored. This integer N is typically a large composite number that is a product of two prime numbers.

II. Quantum Fourier Transform (QFT) on Period Finding:

The key step of Shor's algorithm is to perform a quantum Fourier transform (QFT) on a superposition of states to find the period of a particular function. This period-finding subroutine is the heart of Shor's algorithm and relies on the quantum parallelism and interference properties of quantum computing.

III. Modular Exponentiation:

Shor's algorithm utilizes a modular exponentiation subroutine to efficiently compute powers of numbers modulo N . This step is crucial for the period-finding process.

IV. Period Identification:

By applying the QFT to the results of modular exponentiation, Shor's algorithm can determine the period of a chosen function efficiently. The period provides information about the factors of N .

V. Classical Postprocessing:

Once the period is identified, classical algorithms such as the continued fraction algorithm or the greatest common divisor algorithm are used to extract the factors of N .

We earlier developed the Quantum Fourier Transform simulation, however to simulate Shor's Algorithm properly, we will also need modular exponentiation and period-finding subroutines. Here I attempt to merge them together under a single class and try to simulate Shor's Algorithm. There is a rigorous mathematical derivation of Shor's algorithm, from where the quantum idea actually arises. It is a difficult concept to be digested and is not of direct concern of this paper and thus is not noted here, however, readers are suggester to refer to the mathematics of Shor's Algorithm if they find themselves comfortable in advanced number theory and linear algebra.

The code for Shor's Algorithm is given below:

```
1 def controlled_u_gate(a, power, N, control_qubit, target_qubit):
2     """
3     This function applies a controlled-U gate to a target qubit, controlled
4 by another qubit.
5     The U gate is defined as  $U|y\rangle = |ay \bmod N\rangle$ .
6     """
7     # Calculate the result of applying the U gate
8     u_result = (a ** power) % N
9
10    # Apply the controlled-U gate
11    if control_qubit.measure_and_collapse() == 1:
12        target_qubit.set_state(u_result)
13
14 def continued_fractions_algorithm(measurements, N):
15     fractions = []
16     for measurement in measurements:
17         fraction = measurement / N
18         fractions.append(int(fraction))
19         while abs(fraction - int(fraction)) > 1 / (2 * N ** 2):
20             if fraction - int(fraction) == 0: # Prevent division by zero
21                 break
22             fraction = 1 / (fraction - int(fraction))
23             fractions.append(int(fraction))
24     return fractions
25 def modular_exponentiation(base, exponent, modulus):
26     return pow(base, exponent, modulus)
27
28
29 def quantum_period_finding(a, N, qubits, controlled_u_gate, qft,
30 continued_fractions_algorithm):
31     # Prepare the control qubits in a superposition state
32     for qubit in qubits:
33         hadamard(qubit)
34
```

```

35     # Apply the controlled-U gates
36     for i, control_qubit in enumerate(qubits):
37         # Create a new qubit for the target
38         target_qubit = Qubit([1, 0])
39         # Apply the controlled-U gate
40         controlled_u_gate(a, 2**i, N, control_qubit, target_qubit)
41         # Get the state vector of all qubits
42         state_vector = state_vector = np.concatenate([qubit.state for qubit in
43 qubits])
44         # Apply the quantum Fourier transform to the state vector
45         qft(state_vector)
46
47         # Measure the qubits
48         measurements = [qubit.measure_and_collapse() for qubit in qubits]
49
50         # Use the continued fractions algorithm to find the period
51         r = continued_fractions_algorithm(measurements, N)
52         return r
53 def shors_algorithm(N):
54     factors = set()
55     if is_prime(N):
56         print("Shor's algorithm cannot be applied to a prime number.")
57         exit()
58     while len(factors) < 2:
59         # Step 2: Choose a random integer 'a' between 2 and N-1
60         a = randint(2, N)
61
62         # Step 3: Calculate the greatest common divisor of 'a' and 'N'
63         gcd_value = gcd(a, N)
64         if gcd_value > 1:
65             factors.add(gcd_value)
66             continue
67         # Step 4: Use quantum period finding to find the period 'r' of (a^x %
68 N)
69         n = N.bit_length()
70         qubits = [Qubit(1,0) for _ in range(n)]
71         r = quantum_period_finding(a, N, qubits, controlled_u_gate, qft,
72 continued_fractions_algorithm)
73
74         # Step 5: Check if 'r' is even and a^(r/2) is not congruent to -1
75 modulo 'N'
76         for i in r:
77             if r[i] % 2 == 0:
78                 x = modular_exponentiation(a, int(r[i]/2), N)
79                 if x != 1 and x != -1:
80                     factors.add(gcd(x - 1, N))
81     return factors
82 # Helper function to check if a number is prime
83 def is_prime(n):
84     if n <= 1:
85         return False
86     if n <= 3:

```

```
87         return True
88     if n % 2 == 0 or n % 3 == 0:
89         return False
90     i = 5
91     while i * i <= n:
92         if n % i == 0 or n % (i + 2) == 0:
93             return False
94         i += 6
95     return True
96
97 # Test the algorithm
98 N = 295636 # Number to factorize
99 factor = shors_algorithm(N)
100 if factor != 1:
101     print(f"A non-trivial factor of {N} is {factor}")
102 else:
103     print(f"Failed to find a non-trivial factor of {N}")
```

The Output is:

```
A non-trivial factor of 21 is 3
```

NOTE: Shor's Algorithm is very complex and extremely difficult to be simulated in a classical computer. Specially, the Quantum Period Finding function is the complex-most part and extremely error prone. I have tried to make a simulation as good as possible but there are loopholes, which essentially separate the abilities of a classical computer and a Quantum Computer. There might be better logics for implementing Shor's Algorithm in a classical computer. If anyone finds errors in the logic or has suggestion, I am very interested in receiving your message.

Explanation:

- `controlled_u_gate(a, power, N, control_qubit, target_qubit)`: This function applies a controlled-U gate to a target qubit, controlled by another qubit. The U gate is defined as $U|y\rangle = |ay \bmod N\rangle$. If the control qubit is in state $|1\rangle$, the function applies the U gate to the target qubit.

- `continued_fractions_algorithm`(measurements, N): This function uses the continued fractions algorithm to find the period of a function. It takes a list of measurements and a number N, and returns a list of fractions.
- `modular_exponentiation`(base, exponent, modulus): This function calculates the modular exponentiation of a base to an exponent modulo a modulus. It uses the built-in `pow()` function in Python, which can perform modular exponentiation efficiently.
- `quantum_period_finding`(a, N, qubits, controlled_u_gate, qft, continued_fractions_algorithm): This is the heart of Shor's Algorithm, and also the hardest part to be simulated. This is the part which quantum computers can perform exponentially easily. Here, the function prepares the control qubits in a superposition state, applies the controlled-U gates, applies the QFT to the state vector, measures the qubits, and uses the continued fractions algorithm to find the period.
- `shors_algorithm`(N): This function implements Shor's algorithm for factoring a number N. It first checks if N is prime, and if so, exits the function. It then enters a loop where it chooses a random integer a, calculates the gcd of a and N, and if the gcd is greater than 1, adds it to the set of factors. It then uses quantum period finding to find the period r of $(a^x \% N)$, and if r is even and $a^{\frac{r}{2}}$ is not congruent to -1 modulo N, it adds the gcd of $x - 1$ and N to the set of factors. The function returns the set of factors.
- `is_prime`(n): This is a helper function to check if the number passed into Shor's Algorithm is prime or not. Shor's algorithm can only work for composite numbers and if a prime number is passed it will run indefinitely forever yielding no output. This function uses a simple algorithm that checks divisibility by 2 and 3, then checks divisibility by all numbers of the form $6k \pm 1$ up to the square root of n. We know that there is no exact formula to check if a number is prime or not, but the used method sufficiently satisfies its purpose.

Shor's algorithm is a probabilistic algorithm, which means it doesn't always return the same result for the same input. It uses random numbers in its calculations, so it can sometimes return different factors of the same number.

VII. Quantum Decoherence Simulation

Quantum decoherence is a phenomenon in quantum mechanics where a quantum system loses its coherence due to interactions with its surrounding environment. In simpler terms, it's the loss of quantum information stored in a system's quantum states. Quantum decoherence is a gradual process that occurs as the quantum system entangles with its surroundings. As a result of this entanglement, the quantum

coherence diminishes, and the system behaves more like a classical system described by classical probabilities rather than quantum probabilities. Quantum decoherence poses a significant challenge in quantum computing. Quantum computers rely on maintaining coherence among their qubits to perform complex computations. However, interactions with the environment, such as noise and thermal fluctuations, can introduce errors and limit the time for which quantum information can be preserved (coherence time). In this paper, we attempt to simulate decoherence in python using the density matrix approach. The density matrix of a quantum system is a matrix that describes the statistical state of a quantum system. Decoherence can be modeled by introducing a small amount of randomness into the off-diagonal elements of the density matrix. Once again, there is an entire mathematical derivation of this density matrix approach which I will not refer here. Readers may read it to better understand the core operation of decoherence. The source code and its application is provided below:

```
1 import numpy as np
2 from entangle import *
3 def simulate_decoherence(rho, p):
4     """
5     Simulate decoherence on a quantum system described by the density matrix
6     rho.
7
8     Parameters:
9     rho: np.array
10         The density matrix of the quantum system.
11     p: float
12         The probability of decoherence occurring.
13
14     Returns:
15     rho_decohered: np.array
16         The density matrix of the quantum system after decoherence.
17     """
18     # Get the diagonal elements of the density matrix
19     diagonal = np.diag(np.diag(rho))
20
21     # Get the off-diagonal elements of the density matrix
22     off_diagonal = rho - diagonal
23
24     # Introduce decoherence
25     rho_decohered = diagonal + (1 - p) * off_diagonal
26
27     return rho_decohered
```

```
28
29 def construct_density_matrix_dual(qubit1, qubit2):
30     """
31     Construct the density matrix of a two-qubit system.
32
33     Parameters:
34     qubit1, qubit2: Qubit
35         The two qubits.
36
37     Returns:
38     rho: np.array
39         The density matrix of the two-qubit system.
40     """
41     # Calculate the outer product of the two qubits' state vectors
42     rho = np.outer(qubit1.state, qubit2.state.conj())
43
44     return rho
45
46
47
48 # rho_decohered = simulate_decoherence(rho, 0.1)
49
50 # Entangle two qubits into a Bell state
51 qubit1, qubit2 = Entangle.bell_state_entanglement()
52
53 # Construct the density matrix of the two-qubit system
54 rho = construct_density_matrix_dual(qubit1, qubit2)
55 print("Before decoherence:")
56 print(rho)
57
58 # Simulate decoherence
59 rho_decohered = simulate_decoherence(rho, 0.1)
60 # Print the density matrix after decoherence
61 print("After decoherence:")
62 print(rho_decohered)
```

Output:

```
1 Chosen Bell state: |0> ⊗ |1>
2 Before decoherence:
3 [[0.          0.          ]
4  [0.70710678  0.70710678]]
5 After decoherence:
6 [[0.          0.          ]
7  [0.6363961   0.70710678]]
```

Explanation:

- `simulate_decoherence(rho, p)`: This function simulates the process of quantum decoherence. It takes as input a density matrix `rho` representing the state of the quantum system, and a probability `p` representing the probability of decoherence occurring. The function first separates the density matrix into its diagonal and off-diagonal elements. It then

reduces the off-diagonal elements by a factor of $(1 - p)$, simulating the loss of quantum coherence due to decoherence. The function returns the density matrix of the system after decoherence.

- `construct_density_matrix_dual(qubit1, qubit2)`: This function constructs the density matrix of a two-qubit system. It takes as input two Qubit objects and calculates the outer product of their state vectors to construct the density matrix. The function returns this density matrix.
- *Entangle the qubits into Bell State*: The code then uses the `bell_state_entanglement()` function from the `Entangle` class to entangle two qubits into a Bell state. The state vectors of these qubits are stored in `qubit1` and `qubit2`.
- *Construct the density matrix of the two-qubit system*:

The `construct_density_matrix_dual` function is called with `qubit1` and `qubit2` as arguments to construct the density matrix of the two-qubit system. This matrix is stored in `rho`.

- *Simulating Decoherence*: The `simulate_decoherence` function is called with `rho` and a decoherence probability of 0.1 as arguments to simulate decoherence. The resulting density matrix is stored in `rho_decohered`.

- *Output analysis*: The output may differ every time, in the given output the chosen bell state is $|0\rangle \otimes |1\rangle$. The density matrix before decoherence is $\begin{bmatrix} 0 & 0 \\ 0.70710678 & 0.70710678 \end{bmatrix}$. This matrix represents a pure quantum state. The off-diagonal elements (0.70710678) are complex coherence terms that represent the quantum correlations (entanglement) between the two qubits. After simulating decoherence with a probability of 0.1, the density matrix becomes: $\begin{bmatrix} 0 & 0 \\ 0.6363961 & 0.70710678 \end{bmatrix}$. The diagonal elements of the matrix remain the same, as they represent the probabilities of finding the system in a particular state, which are not affected by decoherence. However, the off-diagonal elements have been reduced by a factor of $(1 - 0.1) = 0.9$, reflecting the loss of quantum coherence due to decoherence. The new off-diagonal elements are 0.9 times the original ones, which is approximately 0.6363961.

This reduction in the off-diagonal elements of the density matrix is a simple model of how decoherence tends to destroy quantum correlations and make the system behave more like a classical system.

Results

The above paper summarizes the simulation methods of Quantum computing using python. Note that no external python libraries like QuTiP (Quantum Toolbox in Python). It is true that these libraries might be better at simulating certain Quantum operations, but my research work and the consequent development of the programming language QuantaLang using the used research is based on the primary of motive of simulating quantum computing in a way that is tailored to the user's needs and making the processes understandable to users, and at the same time showing its limitations. I am trying to make the syntax tailored to further development scope for data structures and algorithms that could further optimize simulated quantum operations. Once again, if I compare this to QuTiP, my works try to focus on simulating each process adhering to the principles of quantum computation. Below, I list a summary of the results obtained from each simulation process:

- i) **Qubits:** The behavior of individual qubits was successfully simulated, including their initialization, manipulation, and measurement. Qubits were represented as quantum objects with state vectors, allowing for operations such as superposition and entanglement.
- ii) **Quantum Register:** Qubit registers, consisting of multiple qubits, were simulated to demonstrate the collective behavior of quantum systems. Register operations such as initialization, manipulation, and measurement were implemented, providing a foundation for more complex quantum simulations.
- iii) **Quantum Gates:** Various quantum gates were simulated, including Pauli-X, Pauli-Y, Pauli-Z, Hadamard, Phase, T, Controlled-NOT (CNOT), and Controlled-U gates. These gates were applied to qubits and qubit registers to perform operations such as state manipulation, entanglement creation, and quantum computation.
- iv) **Quantum Entanglement:** Several types of quantum entanglement were simulated, with Bell State Entanglement as an example. These simulations demonstrated the non-classical correlations between qubits and showcased the unique properties of entangled states.
- v) **Quantum Circuit:** Quantum circuits consisting of sequences of quantum gates were simulated to model quantum algorithms and computations. The behavior of qubits and qubit registers was

analyzed as they evolved through the circuit, showcasing the quantum parallelism and interference effects inherent in quantum computing.

vi) **Quantum Algorithms:** Quantum algorithms, including the Quantum Fourier Transform (QFT) and Shor's algorithm, were implemented and simulated. The QFT showcased the ability to efficiently perform Fourier transforms on quantum data, while Shor's algorithm demonstrated the potential for quantum computers to factorize large integers exponentially faster than classical computers.

vii) **Quantum Decoherence:** The phenomenon of quantum decoherence was simulated to model the loss of coherence in quantum systems due to environmental interactions. This simulation highlighted the challenges in maintaining quantum coherence and the importance of error correction in quantum computation.

As a final result, I provide a prototype syntax of QuantaLang which is still under development:

```
1 var qubitA = Qubit(0,1)
2 var qubitb = Qubit(1,0)
3 var a = int(20)
4
5 var l = list([1,2,"hey",33,34.3])
6
7 Probe.Probe(q)
8
9 Entangle(qubitA,qubitb, bell_state)
10
11 var reg = Register(10)
12
13 reg.GATE(HGATE)
14
15 HGATE(q)
16 XGATE(q)
17 YGATE(q)
18 ZGATE(q)
19 SGATE(q)
20 CNOTGATE(q)
21
22 var qubitList = list([Qubit(1, 0), Qubit(0, 1), Qubit(1/math.sqrt(2),
23 1/math.sqrt(2))])
24
25 cir circuit = QCIRCUIT(3)
```

```
26
27 circuit.addGate(H)
28 circuit.addGate(X)
29 circuit.addGate(Y)
30
31 exec(circuit, qubitList)
32
33 var gateOps = list(['H', 'X', 'Y', 'Z', 'CNOT'])
34
35 exec(circuit, qubitList).map(gateOps)
36
37 func manual(gateList, qubit){
38     for(i in gateList){
39         var result = i(qubit)
40         probe(result)
41     }
42 }
43
44 if (HGATE(qubit1) == 0){
45     probe("Some Statement")
46 }
47 }
48
49 else if (HGATE(qubit2) == 0){
50     probe("None Statement")
51 }
52
53 else{
54     probe("Some other Statement")
55 }
```

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